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WP3B – Overview of materials suitable for application in an ammonia transport infrastructure

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Document summary

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Technology and Safety

- Activities (e.g. maintenance, purging etc.)
- Assets
- Digitalisation
- End use
- Gas network
- QRA

Social aspects

- Conversion (of the distribution network)
- Education
- Social

System and Economy

- Business Development
- Production and supply
- Value chains

Gas Quality

- Admixing
- Gas Quality
- Odourisation

Executive summary

Ammonia has potential as energy carrier for hydrogen transport for the green economy. As such the expectation is that there will be a substantial scale-up in its use. However, there are substantial risks involved. Apart from the comparatively low risk of flammability, the most significant danger is toxicity. This makes it important to be aware of any possible issues when using ammonia in pipelines, especially in cases that they might pass through high density population areas. This report discusses the material compatibility of the current natural gas pipelines with ammonia.

The most significant problem for steel in anhydrous ammonia is stress corrosion cracking. Fortunately, there are steps that can be taken to reduce this effect. These are limiting the strength and weld hardness of piping steel, since softer steels are less susceptible to stress corrosion cracking due to ammonia. Additionally, small quantities of water (0.2-0.5 wt.%) added to the ammonia will inhibit stress corrosion cracking, combined with avoiding the presence of oxygen.

Low-yield strength pipeline steel used for natural gas pipelines is also successfully used for current ammonia pipelines. However, the proposed use of ammonia pipelines as an energy carrier in high density population areas changes the level of acceptable risk. While the base material may be known, the maximum required weld hardness and influence of ammonia on fatigue is not, and as such more research is advised for accurate risk-assessment.

Different sources and standards agree that in order to avoid ammonia stress corrosion cracking the yield strength should be less than 360 MPa. Maximum values for weld hardness differ – the highest limit is 225 HV, which is still quite low. However, these values may be too strict since they do not take the effect of limiting the oxygen content and adding water to the ammonia as used in commercial pipeline ammonia into account.

Alloys commonly used in ammonia pipelines typically have a yield strength of around 400 MPa, which compares well to some mild steels used for natural gas pipelines specified in OSW-01-N, like ASTM A333 grade 6, L245 NE/ME and L290 ME/NE, which have specified yield strength between 240 and 440 MPa. However, some medium strength steels are also used for natural gas pipelines, and would probably be less suitable for use in ammonia as the risk to stress corrosion cracking will increase. Additionally, the weld requirements for anhydrous ammonia pipelines could not be established during this study and therefore cannot be compared to those used for natural gas pipelines. Further investigation is recommended to determine the weld requirements.

When using natural gas pipeline material specification OSW-01-N for future ammonia pipelines, care should be taken to specify that only the low-yield strength pipeline steels should be used.

Since historically stress corrosion due to ammonia has been controlled with the relatively simple measures of limiting the strength and weld hardness of the piping steel, and by adding small quantities of water to the ammonia, the matter is no longer seen as urgent and there has been comparatively little research performed on interactions between ammonia and steel. For this reason there is no data to be found on the effect of anhydrous ammonia on other properties, like fatigue rates and fracture toughness, which are known to be effected by the same environment as stress corrosion cracking.

It must be pointed out that at present most ammonia pipelines are located in areas of low population density. The use of ammonia as an energy carrier would most likely place it in areas of higher density, which would necessarily have an effect on risk assessment. This makes the amount of unknowns – the safe limit for weld hardness and yield strength in commercial ammonia, and the effect on fatigue and fracture toughness - more of an issue.

Note that this report addresses only material compatibility and selection. System requirements and design, risk assessment and maintenance and the like are not within the scope of this study.

Samenvatting

Ammoniak heeft potentie als energietransportmiddel voor de groene economie. De verwachting is dan ook dat het gebruik ervan aanzienlijk zal toenemen. Er zijn echter aanzienlijke risico's aan verbonden. Naast het risico van ontvlambaarheid, is toxiciteit het grootste gevaar van ammoniak. Het is daarom belangrijk om op de hoogte te zijn van mogelijke problemen bij het gebruik van ammoniak in pijpleidingen, vooral in gevallen waarin deze door dichtbevolkte gebieden lopen. In dit rapport wordt de materiële compatibiliteit van de huidige aardgasleidingen met ammoniak besproken.

Het grootste probleem voor staal in watervrije ammoniak is spanningscorrosie. Gelukkig zijn er maatregelen die kunnen worden genomen om dit effect te verminderen. Dit zijn beperken van de sterkte en lashardheid van leidingstaal, omdat zachtere staalsoorten minder gevoelig zijn voor spanningscorrosie door ammoniak. Bovendien zal de toevoeging van kleine hoeveelheden water (0.2-0.5%) aan de ammoniak spanningscorrosie remmen, in combinatie met het vermijden van de aanwezigheid van zuurstof.

Het staal met lage vloeigrens dat wordt gebruikt voor aardgasleidingen, wordt ook met succes toegepast in de huidige ammoniakleidingen. Het voorgestelde gebruik van ammoniakleidingen als energietransportmiddel in dichtbevolkte gebieden verandert echter het niveau van aanvaardbaar risico. Hoewel het basismateriaal bekend is, zijn de maximaal vereiste lashardheid en de invloed van ammoniak op vermoeiing dat niet. Daarom is meer onderzoek nodig voor een nauwkeurige risicobeoordeling.

Verschillende bronnen en normen zijn het erover eens dat de vloeigrens minder dan 360 MPa moet zijn om spanningscorrosie door ammoniak te voorkomen. De maximale waarden voor lashardheid verschillen – de hoogste grens is 225 HV, wat nog steeds vrij laag is. Deze waarden zijn echter mogelijk te streng, omdat ze geen rekening houden met het effect van het beperken van het zuurstofgehalte en het toevoegen van water aan de ammoniak, zoals gebruikt in commerciële pijpleidingen.

Legeringen die vaak worden gebruikt in ammoniakleidingen hebben doorgaans een vloeigrens van ongeveer 400 MPa, wat vergelijkbaar is met sommige zachte staalsoorten die worden gebruikt voor aardgasleidingen gespecificeerd in OSW-01-N, zoals ASTM A333 klasse 6, L245 NE/ME en L290 ME/NE, die een gespecificeerde vloeigrens hebben tussen 240 en 440 MPa. Sommige staalsoorten met gemiddelde sterkte worden echter ook gebruikt voor aardgasleidingen en zouden waarschijnlijk minder geschikt zijn voor gebruik in ammoniak, omdat het risico op spanningscorrosie zal toenemen. Bovendien zijn de lasvereisten voor watervrije ammoniakleidingen niet bekend en kunnen ze daarom niet worden vergeleken met die voor aardgasleidingen.

Bij het gebruik van de aardgasleiding-materiaalspecificatie OSW-01-N voor ammoniak, dient ervoor te worden gezorgd dat uitsluitend pijpleidingstaal met een lage vloeigrens wordt gebruikt.

Omdat spanningscorrosie door ammoniak kan worden bestreden met relatief eenvoudige maatregelen zoals het beperken van de sterkte en lashardheid van het leidingstaal en het toevoegen van kleine hoeveelheden water aan de ammoniak, wordt de kwestie niet langer als urgent beschouwd en is er relatief weinig onderzoek gedaan naar de interacties tussen ammoniak en staal. Om deze reden zijn er geen gegevens te vinden over het effect van vloeibare ammoniak op andere

eigenschappen, zoals vermoeiingssnelheden en breuktaaiheid, waarvan bekend is dat ze worden beïnvloed door dezelfde omstandigheden als spanningscorrosie.

Er moet op worden gewezen dat de meeste ammoniakleidingen zich momenteel in gebieden met een lage bevolkingsdichtheid bevinden. Het gebruik van ammoniak als energiedrager zou het hoogstwaarschijnlijk in gebieden met een hogere bevolkingsdichtheid plaatsen, wat noodzakelijkerwijs van invloed zou zijn op de risicobeoordeling. Dit maakt de hoeveelheid onbekenden – de veilige grens voor lashedheid en vloeigrens in commerciële ammoniak, en het effect op vermoeiing en breuktaaiheid - belangrijker.

Houd er rekening mee dat al het bovenstaande slechts de compatibiliteit en selectie van materialen bespreekt. Systeemvereisten en ontwerp, risicobeoordeling en onderhoud en dergelijke vallen niet binnen het bestek van dit rapport.

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1. Introduction

Ammonia has potential as energy carrier for the green economy since it is easier to store and transport than hydrogen, while being an efficient hydrogen carrier [1]. The expectation is that there will be a substantial scale-up in ammonia trade and transport because of the zero-carbon uses of ammonia, both as a fuel in itself and as a hydrogen-carrier [2].

An advantage of using ammonia is its low boiling point (see figure 1). It can be stored and transported as a liquid at relatively high temperatures compared to natural gas and hydrogen which makes it an efficient energy carrier [3]. That said, many shorter anhydrous (liquid) ammonia pipelines are still operated at cryogenic temperatures, usually $-33\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at low pressures, sometimes even below 10 bar(g) [4]. Longer anhydrous ammonia pipelines operate at ambient temperature, typically around 17 bar(g) [4].

Figure 1: Phase diagram of ammonia [5].

There are substantial risks involved with ammonia. Apart from the risk of flammability, the most significant danger is toxicity. A person will start experiencing negative effects (irritation of mucous membranes) when exposed to concentrations as low as 50 ppm, whereas 1000 ppm ammonia can be deadly [6]. Most current ammonia pipelines are either short distance pipelines in industrial areas, or long distance in rural areas with low population density for ammonia used as fertiliser [4] (interview in Appendix I v). It is therefore important to be aware of any possible issues when transporting ammonia for energy transport, which will pass through high density population areas almost by necessity. There are some indications that existing natural gas pipelines can be used for anhydrous ammonia transport [7], but these have not been confirmed and there is a lack of concrete data. It is important to get more clarity into the question because of the risks involved.

Given the importance of ammonia transport, both currently and in the future, and the risks involved in transporting ammonia it is critical to be sure about material compatibility for anhydrous ammonia pipelines. This is the subject of this report. The focus is on compatibility of pipeline materials with anhydrous ammonia. This is based on literature review (Chapter 2), and standards and known materials already used for anhydrous ammonia pipelines compared to natural gas pipeline materials

(chapter 3). Additional information and context is taken from interviews, a summary of which can be seen in Appendix I. The above covers pipeline. Information of material selection for elastomer packing materials in anhydrous ammonia is given in Appendix II.

Note that all of the above is discussion only of material compatibility and selection. System requirements and design, risk assessment and maintenance and the likes are not within the scope of this report.

2. With the current countermeasures, mild carbon steel piping is mostly resistant to degradation by anhydrous ammonia

Mild carbon steel is typically used for anhydrous ammonia pipelines. Shorter pipelines operate at -33°C and pressures of 2-8 bar(g), while pipelines over 5 km typically operate at ambient temperature with pressures of 15-22 bar(g) to prevent gas formation via boil-off [2].

General corrosion does not pose a significant problem for steel in anhydrous ammonia, but stress corrosion cracking does. There have been a few serious incidents regarding stress corrosion cracking of steel in ammonia, which took place in the 60s and 70s [8]. Following this, steps were taken to prevent similar incidents. These are limiting the strength and weld hardness of piping steel, since softer steels are less susceptible to stress corrosion cracking due to ammonia. Additionally, the presence of oxygen during operation is avoided, and small quantities of water (0.2-0.5%) is added to inhibit stress corrosion cracking [9]. Since implementing these measures with proper maintenance there have been no issues reported with stress corrosion cracking of ammonia pipelines. Incidents that have occurred are similar to those experienced by natural gas pipelines, i.e. damage due to external sources like excavation work, external corrosion and human error [2].

It must be noted that because stress corrosion due to ammonia is controlled by relatively simple measures the matter is no longer seen as urgent and there has been comparatively little research performed on interactions between ammonia and steel since implementation of these measures [3]. For this reason the fundamental mechanisms are not always clear and it is possible that there is more at play that we are not aware of at present. Some details about the possible mechanisms and factors involved are given in Appendix III. Additionally, there is no data to be found of the effect of anhydrous ammonia on other properties, like fatigue rates and fracture toughness, which are known to be effected by the same environment as stress corrosion cracking.

In the next two paragraphs more details are given. In paragraph 2.1 the possible failure mechanisms in steel piping materials are reviewed when ammonia comes into play. In paragraph 2.2 the reason why commercial anhydrous ammonia currently no longer causes cracking in piping steel is explained in further detail.

2.1. Stress corrosion cracking is the most important damage mechanism in ammonia

There are numerous serious damage mechanisms that a given environment can cause in piping materials, for example corrosion fatigue, dealloying and embrittlement. None of these are known to be applicable to steel piping in contact with anhydrous ammonia, which is explained in paragraph 2.1.3. The only known relevant mechanism is ammonia stress corrosion cracking, which mostly takes place in high-tensile strength steel and hard welds, as explained in paragraph 2.1.2. Ammonia is not known to cause any other significant effects on piping steel, although this could be due to a lack of data (paragraph 2.1.3).

2.1.1. Anhydrous ammonia does not pose significant risk of corrosion to piping steel

General corrosion is the most common chemically caused damage mechanism in metals. It is logical that this would also be the main point of concern with a substance like ammonia. However anhydrous ammonia is not substantially corrosive to carbon steel (see 2.1.1.1), although there are a few factors regarding external corrosion and control thereof that need additional attention. These points are briefly discussed in 2.1.1.2.

2.1.1.1. *Anhydrous ammonia does not cause internal corrosion*

Ammonia is generally known as a corrosive substance, mostly because of the aggressivity of various ammonium compounds [10], of which ammonium hydroxide (cleaning ammonia) is the most obvious example. These compounds cause significant corrosion problems in ammonia plants and for various ammonia feedstocks [9].

Pure ammonia is a different issue. Corrosion data shows that carbon steel is 'practically resistant' to a boiling aqueous solution of 25% ammonia [11] but does not give any corrosion rate for anhydrous ammonia. This is likely because the general consensus is that it does not cause any corrosion – in fact carbon and alloy steel stated as being 'fully acceptable for service in anhydrous ammonia' in terms of corrosion [8]. In fact, most metals are resistant to anhydrous ammonia at and around room temperature – stainless steel, magnesium, tin, titanium and zirconium all show no reaction. Of conventional construction metals, only copper alloys and some alloys of aluminium (most significantly those containing copper as alloying element) are not suitable for use in anhydrous ammonia [8]. Based both on corrosion data (as mentioned above) and on experience in the field, carbon steel pipelines have essentially no internal corrosion issues with anhydrous ammonia [4].

2.1.1.2. *There are some additional risks for external corrosion and cathodic protection*

The fact that ammonia itself is not particularly corrosive does not mean there are no challenges involved regarding corrosion. Carbon steel gas pipelines already need protection from external corrosion, which is done by means of a coating (e.g. epoxy and polyethylene) and cathodic protection. This protection is often even more necessary in the case of ammonia pipelines. Many ammonia pipelines operate at cryogenic temperatures, which carries additional risks for external corrosion due to condensation [4]. In the case of such pipelines, more care must be taken with corrosion protection than usually would be the case. Granted, anhydrous ammonia pipelines for energy transport will be longer than typical cryogenic pipelines, and so will most likely operate at ambient temperature, with a slightly higher pressure to compensate.

There may be an additional complication for ammonia pipelines compared to natural gas when it comes to external corrosion, namely the effect on cathodic protection. Cathodic protection is used for ammonia pipelines [1, 12] but it is not clear if the same set-up can be used for ammonia as for natural gas. Natural gas has a low electrical conductivity, and as such the effective cathodic protection current can be measured across two electrically insulated pipe segments, without leakage current. Moreover, insulating joints can ensure an electrical separation between the cathodic protected pipeline and another object. Pure ammonia has a very low electrical conductivity of $0.13 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at -79°C [13], however no hard data could be found on the electrical conductivity of commercial grade ammonia. There is an off-hand mention that the conductivity of ammonia is low, in the context of the effectiveness of a protective zinc coating [14], but no mention is made of the purity of ammonia referred to or what is classified as 'low'. The expectation is that the small amounts of additions and impurities would significantly increase the electrical conductivity. For comparison, tap water typically has a conductivity of approximately $500 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, and seawater $42\,000 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ [15]. If the conductivity of commercial anhydrous ammonia is substantially higher than that of natural gas, the effectiveness of insulating joints may diminish significantly. It may therefore be necessary to adjust (critical) insulating joints in the cathodic protection to a system similar to that which is used for water pipe systems in order to avoid the issues caused by conductivity of the medium.

Additionally, if commercial grade ammonia is sufficiently conductive it may also become necessary to take additional measures to protect against corrosion due to stray current from tram tracks, high-voltage systems, solar parks and similar. A conductive medium (as anhydrous ammonia potentially

might be) makes for longer electrically conductive pipe sections, which is one of the parameters for stray current influence due to high voltage systems. NEN 3654 [16] contains recommendations and safe distances from sources of AC stray current, should this prove to be relevant.

2.1.2. Anhydrous ammonia causes stress corrosion cracking in steel and hard welds

Carbon and alloy steels are known to suffer stress corrosion cracking (SCC) in anhydrous ammonia. Stress corrosion cracking is a process by which the combination of tensile stress (externally caused or residual stress from welding and fabrication) and an alloy-environment combination that causes spontaneous crack formation in the metal [2]. All three factors – stress, susceptible metal, and causative environment – have to be present in order for cracking to occur. This is commonly shown in the Venn-diagram in figure 2. It shows the various factors influencing the possibility that stress corrosion cracking may occur and how severe it will be, like composition, microstructure, temperature, nature of the stress involved etc.

Figure 2: Stress Corrosion Cracking (SCC) and the various factors that influence it [17].

Carbon steels like ASTM A106 grade B, ASTM A285 grade C and ASTM A515 grade 70 are all known to be susceptible to various kinds of stress corrosion cracking [12]. The rate of crack initiation and propagation depends on the metallurgical condition of the metal, impurities in the environment and the type and magnitude of loading on the material [2].

High strength steel is more susceptible to cracking in ammonia than low strength steel, as are hard welds. The risk of cracking scales with the yield strength, and with the hardness of the weld [2].

In general the stress needed for stress corrosion cracking of steel in anhydrous ammonia is high and not experienced in piping during normal operation. However, for hard welds and high strength steels the combination of residual stress and stresses due to operation may be enough to initiate stress corrosion cracking [4]. Most failures attributed to ammonia stress corrosion cracking has been with non-stress-relieved higher-strength quenched and tempered steels, such as the grades covered in ASTM A517 [12].

It must be noted that yield strength and weld hardness are used as easily measurable short-hands for susceptibility, but different microstructures and heat-treatments are susceptible to ammonia stress corrosion cracking at different hardnesses. For example, very fine bainitic steel has a higher

resistance to ammonia stress corrosion cracking than that other microstructures of same strength and hardness. Quenched steel resists cracking at a hardness of 260 HV, while the same steel in a quenched and tempered state is susceptible at 200 HV [3]. As such, higher strength steels with good resistance to ammonia stress corrosion cracking have been developed for situations where other mitigating processes fail.

The strong effect of microstructure and heat treatment are the reason why in practice ammonia stress corrosion cracking often takes place at the welds, where there is substantial changes in microstructure due to heat-input during welding. Cracks tend to initiate as transgranular cracks in the weld metal, becoming intergranular as they grow into the coarse grained heat-affected zone [14]. This can be avoided by using soft welding materials [14] and thermal stress relief to reduce the likelihood of crack formation [8]. Heat treatment of at least 650°C is advised for effective stress relief after welding [12]. Hard grinding after welding must also be avoided [14].

Additionally, ammonia stress corrosion cracking in steel mainly takes place at ambient temperatures [2]. It is rare below 0°C and almost unheard of at -33°C [12] (a common temperature for ammonia pipelines) [2], only taking place with very susceptible metals and certain grades of ammonia [12].

2.1.3. There is little research on the effect of anhydrous ammonia other properties of piping steel

Apart from very low general corrosion and significant stress corrosion cracking, no other damage mechanisms are mentioned in regard to steel and anhydrous ammonia. This is notable because in general corrosion fatigue and stress corrosion cracking are known to be related [18], and circumstances that cause stress corrosion cracking will tend to cause corrosion fatigue when dynamic loading is present. However, no mention could be found in the literature regarding corrosion fatigue in steel and anhydrous ammonia, or any other relevant damage mechanism like fracture toughness. This is likely at least partially due to a lack of research [3](interview in Appendix I v), and not because there is absolutely no effect. More research is needed to know what the extent of the effect of anhydrous ammonia on the corrosion fatigue and fracture toughness of steel is, if any.

2.2. Currently, commercial anhydrous ammonia is not known to cause cracking in piping steel

Stress corrosion cracking due to anhydrous ammonia is a serious issue and has caused a number of incidents in the past [8]. Since then, research has been performed to identify the reasons underlying this issue. Based on this, several measures have been put in place to avoid crack formation, e.g. by controlling the composition of commercial ammonia (see paragraph 2.2.1) and by limiting the material strength and weld hardness. This effectively controls ammonia stress corrosion cracking, and no issues are known to have come up in service since then [4]. More details can be found in paragraph 2.2.2.

2.2.1. The composition of commercial ammonia is controlled in order to prevent cracking

The degree of stress corrosion cracking in steel due to anhydrous ammonia is strongly influenced by the presence of additives in the medium, most notably oxygen and water; but carbon dioxide and nitrogen also play a role [3]. Stress corrosion cracking of steel in anhydrous ammonia will only take place in the presence of oxygen [4]. Even a single ppm oxygen during operation [7] can be enough to initiate the effect, and the more oxygen, the stronger the effect. It is in cases with high oxygen content where stress corrosion cracking could take place at temperatures below 0°C, or due to residual stresses only [4]. This effect can be resolved by small additions of water to inhibit stress

corrosion cracking [12]. The balance between effect of oxygen and water can be seen in figure 3. The sensitivity to oxygen is why the commissioning period is the most critical period with respect to stress corrosion cracking [14], and the reason why systems intended for anhydrous ammonia are often flushed with nitrogen before use (interview in Appendix I iii).

Figure 3: Stress corrosion cracking susceptibility as function of oxygen and water content at 18°C [14].

The effect of nitrogen and carbon dioxide is more subtle. Different studies find different results. Carbon dioxide may either help cause or inhibit stress corrosion cracking, and it seems that nitrogen and oxygen cause cracking together, although it is unclear if nitrogen would cause cracking without the presence of oxygen [3].

These days commercial grade ammonia has between 0.2 and 0.5 wt.% water added to reduce the effect of stress corrosion cracking [2].

2.2.2. Failures of ammonia pipelines are no longer caused by stress corrosion cracking

There have been a quite a few serious incidents regarding stress corrosion cracking during the period when large scale use and transport of ammonia first started. In 1968 an ammonia tank in France ruptured, killing 5, and in 1973 an ammonia tank in South Africa failed, leading to 22 deaths [8]. Thankfully pipelines are usually built in low population density areas. However, this is not always the case, and population spread in recent years means that some pipelines that were initially built in low population areas now run through high population areas [2]. These aging pipelines pose a problem. An analysis of 232 ammonia pipeline incidents occurring between 1970 and 2023 in the US reveals that a significant proportion of failures were directly linked to material defects or issues related to welding [19]. This highlights that fabrication quality and post-weld treatments are critical to maintaining pipeline safety, and regular monitoring are combined to reduce risk and ensure long-term pipeline reliability.

Analysis of the pipeline incidents show that material or welding defects (36%) and equipment failures (26%) constitute the primary failure types of ammonia pipelines. As can be seen in figure 4, the incidents have been increasing per 1000 km pipeline over time [19]. It is only during the last ten years that the failure frequency has gone down, reflecting developing standards in maintenance and monitoring, as well as the increased quality of new systems [2, 19].

Figure 4: Failure frequency of ammonia pipelines in the US per 1000 km including 5 year moving average. [19]

In modern anhydrous ammonia pipelines proper control of material selection and weld hardness is implemented, along with risk-management, maintenance and monitoring. These improvements, combined with control of the composition of the medium itself, has caused that stress corrosion cracking is no longer reported as a problem in anhydrous ammonia pipelines [4].

Currently typical causes of failures in ammonia pipelines are caused by external corrosion, systems failures (e.g. overpressure), external damage (human error), equipment failure and fatigue, as is the case in natural gas pipelines [2, 4]. An example of this is the case of an ammonia pipeline in Mexico, which failed due to damage by excavation work in 2013, necessitating the evacuation of 1500 people and ending in at least nine fatalities [2].

3. Some current natural gas pipeline materials are similar to anhydrous ammonia pipeline materials

There is a reasonable amount of data available on the effect on anhydrous ammonia on steel, as highlighted in chapter 2 and appendix III. While this is helpful in general terms, more precise guidance is needed for appropriate material selection. Various studies advise limiting the yield strength to 360 MPa [7] or 370 MPa, or indicate that the hardness threshold is somewhere around 200 HV depending on the alloy and circumstances [3]. However, it would be more appropriate to consider the requirements for various ammonia piping standards, as these have to take real-world circumstances into account. It is found that most standards also generally specify a maximum yield strength, as discussed in paragraph 3.1. Only ASME B31.4 provides a list of materials to choose from. Paragraph 3.2 therefore compares the alloys that are applied in practice to transport anhydrous ammonia, with conventional natural gas pipeline materials. It is found that ASTM A333 grade 6, L245 NE/ME, L290 ME/NE compare well to alloys used in anhydrous ammonia pipelines. Unfortunately, the weld requirements for anhydrous ammonia pipelines are not known and cannot be compared to those used for natural gas pipelines.

3.1. Requirements for anhydrous ammonia pipelines

The most relevant standard for Dutch steel piping systems is NEN 3650 – Requirements for pipeline Systems [20] [21]. This standard mentions that care should be taken in terms of corrosion and stress corrosion cracking, with general recommendations with regards to internal coatings, corrosion inhibitors, cathodic protection and the like. However, there are no specific requirements mentioned for ammonia. There is more specific information to be found in PGS 12 from the Dutch series of publications on hazardous substances [6]. The section on piping only mentions suitability for low temperature in terms of material selection. Fortunately, there are more relevant requirements in the section of PGS 12 for materials for ammonia tanks in order to avoid stress corrosion cracking in carbon steel. These are as follows:

- limit the yield strength to between 290 and 360 MPa;
- use a weld filler with a strength not substantially higher than the strength of the plate material;
- hardness in the weld must be tested and may not be higher than 225 HV;
- welding to be performed according to ISO 15614-1 or the relevant product standard. [6]

Welding according to ISO 15614-1 is subject to similar restrictions, wherein it is advised that in situations where carbon steel is subject to stress corrosion cracking the yield strength should not be higher than 360 MPa [22].

These requirements are in line with various different national and international standards and recommendations for ammonia systems which generally specify a maximum yield strength of 350 MPa (for example in British and Finnish standards) [14], 360 MPa (as previously mentioned for Dutch standards [6]), 370 MPa (international shipping standards [23]) or 400 MPa¹ (Dutch requirements for rail transport [24]) respectively. These are all requirements for steel in contact with anhydrous ammonia, but not specifically for pipelines.

This leaves one significant standard to be discussed, namely ASME B31.4 – Pipeline Transportation Systems for Liquids and Slurries, which explicitly mentions anhydrous ammonia and is internationally

¹ If the yield strength is higher than 400 MPa, the material is subject to periodical examination by means of magnetic particle in order to check for crack formation.

used for this application [4, 25]. Unlike previously mentioned standards, it does not explicitly specify a maximum yield strength, but instead provides a list of materials to choose from. This is the same list (copied below in table 1) ASME B31.4 gives for any other liquid or slurry pipeline, apart from the mention that alloys with high copper content (over 0.4%) are not suitable for use in ammonia, and some additional requirements for welds.²

Note that while ASME B31.4 specifies material grade and post-weld heat-treatment, it is not necessarily the case that these will result in conformity to the hardness and yield strength requirements of PGS 12 and similar standards, since the alloys listed in table 1 are a mix of low and medium strength carbon steels, none of which specify a maximum for yield strength, only a minimum, and so could easily have a yield strength significantly higher than 360 MPa. Since ASME B31.4 mentions that all aspects of stress corrosion cracking have not been taken into account and advises the user to refer to the current state of the art, it would seem that stress corrosion cracking due to ammonia is not taken into account in material list. That returns us to the question of the state of the art, i.e. what alloys are used in current anhydrous ammonia pipelines?

Table 1: Carbon steel specified for liquid and slurry pipelines in table 423.1-1 of ASME B31.4 [25]

API 5L	Line pipe, PSL 2 is recommended
ASTM A53	Pipe, Steel, Black & Hit-Dipped, Zinc-Coated & Seamless
ASTM A106	Seamless Carbon Steel Pipe for High-Temperature Service
ASTM A134	Pipe, Steel, Electric-Fusion (Arc) Welded (Sizes NPS 16 and Over)
ASTM A135	Electric-Resistance-Welded Steel Pipe
ASTM A139	Electric-Fusion (Arc)-Welded Steel Pipe (NPS 4 and Over)
ASTM A333	Seamless and Welded Steel Pipe for Low Temperature Service
ASTM A381	Metal-Arc Welded Steel Pipe for Use With High-Pressure Transmission Systems
ASTM A524	Seamless Carbon Steel Pipe for Atmospheric and Lower Temperatures
ASTM A530	General Requirements for Specialized Carbon and Alloy Steel Pipe
ASTM A671	Electric-Fusion-Welded Steel Pipe for Atmospheric and Lower Temperatures
ASTM A672	Electric-Fusion-Welded Steel Pipe High-Pressure Service at Moderate Temperature

3.2. Steel alloys used in practice in anhydrous ammonia pipelines

Given the amount of alloys listed in ASME B31.4 for anhydrous ammonia pipelines, it is of interest to know which of these are applied in practice, and how these materials compare to conventional natural gas pipeline materials. There are indications that in some cases natural gas pipeline materials may be used for anhydrous ammonia [14], although this is not the case for all natural gas pipeline materials, and certainly not for all pipeline configurations [7].

The materials used for anhydrous ammonia pipelines are uniformly low-strength carbon steel, although the specific alloys differ. ASTM A333 grade 6 is very commonly used, both in natural gas pipelines and in anhydrous ammonia pipelines in the Netherlands, Portugal and Spain (both for ambient and low temperature pipelines, with pressures ranging from 3.5 to 18 bar) [1, 4].

² ASME B31.4 requires that for anhydrous ammonia pipelines all longitudinal or helical seam welds of electric resistance welded and electric induction welded pipe shall be normalized. While there is no hardness requirement mentioned, normalizing is a high-temperature post-weld heat-treatment intended to completely reduce weld hardness while keeping sufficient toughness and a fine-grain structure [37]. It is a substantially more rigorous treatment than stress-relief or tempering.

Note that these are all pipelines of 10 km or shorter. The longest anhydrous ammonia pipeline in Western Europe is in Italy, which uses either API 5L Grade B [4] or API 5L X52N [1] (sources disagree and the truth of the matter could not be determined). This is a significant difference, since API 5L grade B is low strength grade similar to ASTM A333 grade 6, while API 5L X52N is a medium strength alloy, which in at least one case was found not to be suitable for transporting ammonia due to numerous failures due to stress corrosion cracking [26]. Note that both these alloys are allowed according to ASME B31.4.

The significant difference between the requirement stated in multiple standards, and the materials currently used in practice for ammonia pipelines (that may have a higher yield strength) may be because nowadays anhydrous ammonia in pipelines has the often required 0.2 and 0.5 wt.% water, which limits the occurrence of stress corrosion cracking. There may be a higher limit for hardness and yield strength than in ammonia without added water, but there is no data on exactly what this higher limit may be. ASTM A333 grade 6 and API 5L Grade B will typically have a yield strength around 400 MPa (based on the specified minimum of 240 MPa), although this can vary in practice. At present there does not seem to be any indication that recent pipelines of these alloys suffer failures that can be ascribed to stress corrosion cracking. Granted, there are a relatively low amount of modern anhydrous ammonia pipelines, and most of these are 10 km or shorter [4]. American pipelines are typically much longer (hundreds of kilometres) and new pipelines are reported as using ASTM A53 grade B and ASTM A106 grade B [1]. These pipe grades are also low strength steels. A comparison between the specified yield strength of known anhydrous pipeline materials and natural gas pipeline steels are given in table 2 below.

Table 2: Comparison of pipeline materials - anhydrous ammonia and natural gas.

Material Grade	Yield Strength as specified	Known Current Application
ASTM A333 grade 6³	≥ 240 / 245 – 440 MPa	Ammonia / Natural gas pipelines
API 5L Grade B	≥ 240 MPa	Ammonia pipelines
ASTM A53 grade B	≥ 240 MPa	Ammonia pipelines
ASTM A106 grade B	≥ 240 MPa	Ammonia pipelines
API 5L X52N	≥ 360 MPa	Ammonia pipelines, reportedly
L245 NE/ME⁴	245 – 440 MPa	Natural gas pipelines
L290 ME/NE⁴	290 – 440 MPa	Natural gas pipelines
L360ME/NE⁴	360 – 515 MPa	Natural gas pipelines
L415 ME⁴	415 – 535 MPa	Natural gas pipelines
L485 ME⁴	485 – 580 MPa	Natural gas pipelines

As can be seen in table 2, there is considerable overlap in materials commonly used for natural gas pipelines, and anhydrous ammonia pipelines, but natural gas pipelines also apply medium strength carbon steel that does not compare well to currently used ammonia pipeline steel and should probably be avoided. Note that ASME B31.4 lists materials with similar yield strength, but ASME B31.4 might not take stress corrosion cracking due to ammonia sufficiently into account (as explained in paragraph 3.1).

Additionally, there is a lack of information on which (if any) post-weld heat-treatment and/or required maximum hardness is used for anhydrous ammonia piping. Based on literature and the

³ Yield strength values are taken from the Gasunie internal standard MSW-01-E/2, as referred to in OSW-01-N.

⁴ Yield strength values are taken from the Gasunie internal standard MSW-01-E as referred to in OSW-01-N.

requirement for ammonia tanks and similar applications, the welds should receive at least a stress-relief heat treatment, but once again there is no data on what a suitable value would be. This makes it unclear if current natural gas pipes could be used as anhydrous ammonia pipelines.

When using natural gas pipeline material specifications for future pipelines, care should be taken to specify that only low-yield strength pipeline steel like ASTM A333 grade 6, L245 NE/ME and L290 ME/NE (with post-weld heat-treatment) should be used for ammonia pipelines. If specific data becomes available on the susceptibility of pipeline steels of higher yield to pipeline quality ammonia becomes available it may be possible to allow steels with higher yield, but with current knowledge that does not seem prudent.

Appendix I – Interview questions and answers

The following set of questions were selected for the interviews. Not every question was relevant for every interview, and not all questions were fully answered. This is just to indicate which topics were covered during the discussions.

- What does the ammonia infrastructure look like in general? Specifically focusing on the pipelines.
- Approximately how many kilometres of pipelines are on site? Is part of it underground or above ground?
- At what pressures and temperatures is ammonia transported through the pipelines?
- What is the composition of the ammonia? –
 - Any contaminants, e.g. N₂, O₂, CO₂?
 - How is the minimum amount of water in the ammonia guaranteed? (Depending on the supplier or self-monitoring?)
- What material(s) are the pipeline systems made of?
 - Extends to coatings, type of material, gaskets etc. Which alloys, standards, welding procedures?
 - Are the same types of materials used for ammonia and natural gas?
 - What supplier supplies the material?
 - What is the maximum hardness for steel pipes? Is this also relevant for welding?
 - Requirements for gaskets? Which ones are used?
- How much maintenance is required on the existing pipes?
 - Is any damage found? If so, what is the effect of this damage on the material? Is there corrosion in the pipes?
 - Are there any preventative inspections? – Replacement once a month/year/5 years
- Have any materials-specific problems been observed with ammonia transport through pipes over the years?
- Can they help us further with contacts at companies/individuals who have more knowledge of ammonia transport?

i. Results of discussion with Mannesmann representatives

Interview with Holger Brauer and Manuel Simm from Mannesmann (producer of steel piping) on 10-07-2025.

The following statements were made:

- They have produced carbon steel piping for ammonia pipelines – these were the alloys P235 and L360 with an additional requirement for Charpy V-notch test at -40 °C.
- They have also produced carbon steel piping for ammonia pipelines according to ASTM A333 grade 4 and grade 6.
- There were no special requirements for longitudinal welds – they have the same requirements as the base material.
- Piping was delivered according to ASME B31.12 (Hydrogen Piping and Pipelines).
- The same material is delivered for above ground and underground piping. The only difference is the thermal insulation with aluminium used for above ground piping.
- Polyurethane is also used for thermal insulation for cryogenic pipes.
- UNIPER is planning ammonia transport in the North sea with a terminal at Willemshaven.
- A large ammonia project is being developed in Morocco.

ii. Results of discussion with SoluForce representative

Interview with Peter Cloos from SoluForce (producer of flexible composite piping) on 25-08-2025.

The following statements were made:

- SoluForce produces piping that is typically used at 40-80 bar, but some of their designs can be used up to 200 bar.
- Piping consists of HDPE with aramid or steel wire reinforcement, in 4 and 6 inch diameters.
- Eight inch diameter piping is being developed.
- Advantages of SoluForce piping include low maintenance, low carbon footprint, and ease of installation.
- Another advantage is that even when damage occurs, SoluForce pipes cannot tear open and cause large scale leaks of the kind that may happen with bulk materials.
- No embrittlement was found in the steel wires during NACE tests.
- SoluForce piping may be used for hydrogen up to 25 bar.
- SoluForce are working with Fluxys on piping for hydrogen up to 100 bar.
- SoluForce has a lot of pipelines installed for hydrogen applications, for example in Switzerland.
- SoluForce piping is tested according to API 15S, which involves chemical compatibility (but not permeation), rapid decompression testing, and impact testing.
- Possible problems with using SoluForce piping for ammonia would be permeation and chemical compatibility in the sense of solubility and diffusion.
- Solubility and diffusion in ammonia could also give problems in regard to rapid decompression.
- Unfortunately testing facilities tend to be unwilling to test with ammonia.
- The quality/composition is an added complication for compatibility (e.g. additions of water, NO_x, sulfuric acid, nitric acid)
- Aluminium can be used as an internal anti-permeation layer.
- Based on tests performed, SoluForce piping can be used at temperatures down to -33 °C.
- Daniel van Leeuwen at Eriks is a possible contact person for information on gaskets in ammonia

iii. Results of discussion with ISPT representative

Interview with Rob Stevens from ISPT (Institute for Sustainable Process Technology) on 27-08-2025

The following statements were made:

- Before joining ISPT as program director, Rob Stevens worked for Yara and has 24 years of experience in the field.
- There are long distance ammonia pipelines in Russia and UK, Yara has installed a pipeline of approximately 80 km in Italy, a couple of hundred meters in Norway, and 5 km in Western Australia.
- Sections of ammonia piping from and to storage are at cryogenic temperatures. In most cases these are always kept filled with ammonia to avoid problems with oxygen, but some companies consider it safe enough to empty these sections between uses.
- Ammonia pipelines are not at high pressure, the medium is just pumped around.
- Ammonia must be kept free of oxygen to avoid Stress corrosion cracking, which is known because of historical failures.

- Best practice is to add 2000 ppm water to ammonia and perform analysis to check the quality.
- General carbon steel already known as piping material is used for ammonia piping.
- External corrosion can be a problem – an inspection program is needed.
- Ammonia pipeline contractors tend to have a list of suitable gasket materials. This is part of maintenance.
- Internal corrosion for ammonia pipelines is generally avoided due to the risks of oxygen contact. In some cases pipelines are flushed with nitrogen and inspected internally with a robot when necessary.
- Leakages rarely occur in these pipelines, and when they do they are quickly detected with glass fibre sensors.
- Avoid flanges because they can cause stresses due to temperature effects and differentials. Use welds where possible instead.
- Proton Ventures does engineering for ammonia terminals, like the one in Schiedam which done according to PGS 12. They are a possible source of information on packing materials. Hans Vrijenhoef and Kevin Kardux are possible points of contact.

Further information:

- Ammonia pipelines are flushed with nitrogen to clear at oxygen before commissioning.
- The industry is restrained in depressurizing ammonia pipelines due to risks of air/oxygen ingress, so inspection intervals need to be as long as possible.
- Ammonia pipelines at shipping terminals are also kept pressurised as long as is feasible between loading/unloading to prevent oxygen ingress.

iv. Results of discussion with ERIKS representatives

Interview with Arien Jager and Paul Lemmens (sealing O-Rings/ gaskets supplier) on 30-10-2025.

The following statements were made:

- Rubber components commonly used in ammonia transport include O-Rings, gaskets and flame gaskets.
- Ammonia becomes liquid at approximately 8-12 bar. When operating at ambient temperature, expecting working pressures typically range between 15-20 bar.
- Typical transmission gas grid pressures (50-80 bar according to ISO 11114-2) are not expected for liquid ammonia.
- ISO 23936-2 (*Petroleum, petrochemical and natural gas industries – non-metallic material in contact with media related to oil and gas production – Part 2: Elastomers*) specifies a RGD of 0000 rating. However, this standard is designed for gas pipelines and may need adaptation for liquid ammonia.
- Neoprene (CR) was used for sealing applications involving ammonia in the past. EPDM is now recommended for ammonia contact.
- FFKM is compatible with ammonia but unnecessary for 15-20 bars at ambient temperature and is significantly more expensive.
- Recommended sealing solution: EPDM O-Rings (ERIKS suggested: EPDM 559037)
- Flange gaskets (ERIKS suggested: KV9/KV9L) made of stainless steel 304 and PTFE (Polytetrafluoroethylene), which are safe and economical option.
- There are other companies working with ammonia in the market. They mainly work with fertilizers; they are using stainless steel 304 for pipes and PTFE for gaskets.

v. Results of discussion with Mannesmann representatives

Interview with Christoph Weil, Manuel Müller and Holger Brauer of Mannesmann (producer of steel piping) and Thomas Haase (SZMF/EDWK) on 11-11-2025.

The following statements were made:

- Mannesmann delivered approximately 1 ammonia pipeline in 10 years.
- German papers from the 70's may have additional information on steel/ammonia interactions.
- Carbon steel with strength up to the level of X52 is OK for use in ammonia as long as there is a sufficient addition of water to reduce the effect of stress corrosion cracking.
- There are a lot of long distance pipelines in the US and Russia which do experience occasional failures, but these are uncontrolled pipelines with bad maintenance / monitoring and external damage.
- Standards for ammonia include API, compressed gas USA, and standard for rail transport.
- Japan is moving to burn ammonia directly instead of changing to hydrogen and might be making an ISO standard for this application.
- Non-seamless ASTM A333 from Mannesmann was used for an ammonia pipeline in Algeria in 2008. Stress analysis for this project was performed according to ASME B31.3.
- IFA in Norway has helpful publications on ammonia pipelines.
- TK70 epoxy coating can be applied in the field and is used in offshore piping.
- ISO TC 67 is adding a section on ammonia.
- Longer ammonia pipelines tend to have higher pressures in order to be able to reduce the amount of booster stations.

Appendix II – Elastomers in anhydrous ammonia

The most suitable elastomers for gaseous ammonia service are chloroprene rubber (CR, neoprene), butyl rubber (IIR) and ethylene propylene diene monomer rubber (EPDM), as recommended by ISO 11114-2 [27] and elastomer O-rings application suppliers [28, 29]. However, for ammonia transportation in the liquid state, where operating pressures and temperatures are comparatively lower than for gas state, EPDM may be a suitable solution [30] and considering its cost-effectiveness, the use of EPDM O-rings are recommended for this application.

For gas transportation, according to ISO 11114-2 - *Gas cylinders: Compatibility of cylinder and valve materials with gas contents- Part 2* [27], elastomeric components in contact with gaseous ammonia must withstand operating pressures between 50 and 80 bar and temperatures ranging from -20 °C to +50 °C. In addition, O-ring materials must pass Rapid Gas Decompression (RGD) testing with a 0000 rating, indicating no blistering or structural damage, in accordance with ISO 23936-2 - *Petroleum, petrochemical and natural gas industries: Non-metallic materials in contact with media related to oil and gas production - Part 2: Elastomers* [31]. However, in the case of liquid ammonia state (anhydrous ammonia), transportation occurs at lower pressures, approximately 15-22 bar(g) at ambient temperature [2, 4], rather than the 50–80 bar(g) typical for gas transportation. It should also be noted that the RGD 0000 rating test is designed for gas-phase applications and therefore may not directly represent the behaviour of elastomeric O-rings when exposed to ammonia in liquid form. For pressures up to 50-80 bar rubber application should be reconsidered.

Material compatibility is critical because anhydrous ammonia is highly aggressive toward many conventional rubbers. Exposure to incompatible elastomers can cause swelling [28, 29] and embrittlement, losing their flexibility [32]. To ensure safe operation, selected materials must resist ammonia's polar, basic, and permeating characteristics. In general, rubbers such as nitrile (NBR) exhibit poor resistance to ammonia due to their vulnerability to alkaline attack [33]. Conversely, EPDM and CR, demonstrate superior performance because of their polarity and inherent chemical stability. The choice of elastomer in ammonia systems depends heavily on operating pressure, temperature, chemical compatibility, and exposure duration. These factors determine the long-term reliability, safety, and sealing performance of critical components such as gaskets, O-rings, and valve seals.

Overall, elastomer selection for ammonia transportation systems must align with the specific service conditions to ensure safe, durable, and leak-free operation.

Appendix III – Possible mechanisms behind ammonia stress corrosion cracking

Since stress corrosion cracking of steel by anhydrous ammonia can be controlled by the simple means of adding water and limiting the material strength, there has been little reason for further research into the fundamental mechanisms involved in ammonia stress corrosion cracking [3].

The mechanism of stress corrosion cracking is believed to involve an environment that promotes the formation of a unstable film [3]. In the case of carbon and alloy steel and ammonia, the film in question is a nitride layer [12], and nitrides form at the crack tip of the stress corrosion crack. The theory is that crack growth takes place due to stress breaking the brittle nitrides [7] at the crack tip [18], exposing fresh material surface for further crack growth, see figure 5.

Figure 5: Stress corrosion cracking of steel in an ammonia tank wall [7].

Additionally, ammonia stress corrosion cracking in steel mainly takes place at ambient temperatures [2]. It is rare below 0°C and almost unheard of at -33°C [12], only taking place with very susceptible metals and certain grades of ammonia [12]. This is thought to be because the scale that stress corrosion cracking is dependent on forms less readily at low temperature [3].

It is known that oxygen is needed for ammonia stress corrosion cracking to occur [4], but the mechanism by which oxygen induces SCC is unclear. It has been suggested to act by disturbing the nitride layer, or oxidizing surface iron atoms and/or by creating a unstable mixed metal scale on the surface [3] [7]. In contrast a small addition of water stabilises the scale [3].

The scale can also be affected in other ways. Some steel alloys (like Q370DR) inherently form a more stable film and as such are not susceptible to ammonia stress corrosion cracking [34]. Metal oxide coatings, generally used for corrosion protection, also provide a stable film and are effective against ammonia stress corrosion cracking [7].

In contrast, it has been found that steel that has been allowed to rust before starting ammonia service is more susceptible to cracking [14]. This is likely because rust is inherently an unstable scale.

It is also possible to avoid scale formation (and therefore cracking) altogether by using a zinc-spray coating [2]. This is often used around welds in ammonia tanks with great success [14], where the coating typically has a lifetime of 5-10 years [3].

There is also the theory that stress corrosion cracking by ammonia is not a form of stress corrosion cracking at all, but a subset of hydrogen embrittlement [35]. This theory came about due to the metallurgical precautions to avoid ammonia stress corrosion cracking are the same as the precautions to avoid hydrogen embrittlement in sour service (natural gas with wet H₂S). The presumed mechanism is that through appropriate combinations of oxygen and water the oxidation-reduction can take place at the steel surface with oxygen acting as in intermediate oxidiser:

This reaction is also known to take place in high temperature anhydrous ammonia [7].

There are some test results that seem to imply that this is indeed the case [36], but this has not been confirmed, and the reaction between ammonia and steel is still referred to as stress corrosion cracking. This is mostly because the distinction between hydrogen embrittlement and stress corrosion cracking used to be made based on electrochemical conditions, with stress corrosion cracking being enhanced with anodic polarisation and hydrogen embrittlement being enhanced by cathodic polarisation, even though in both cases the mechanism is often similar [37]. Because cracking due to ammonia is anodic in nature, it is therefore defined as stress corrosion cracking, and the previous description of unstable scale formation stands [3]. However, the reaction described in [35] is also referred to as anodic in nature, leaving some doubt as to the proper definition.

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